

FUNCTIONAL-SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF COMPLEX SENTENCES WITHOUT CONJUNCTIONS IN MODERN KARAKALPAK LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The article explores the structure and meaning of complex sentences in the Karakalpak language that do not use conjunctions. It aims to understand how these sentences are constructed and how they convey meaning without traditional conjunctions. The analysis involves examining the syntactic structure of these sentences and identifying the different types of clauses and their relationship within the sentence. It also involves analyzing the semantic roles and relationships expressed within these sentences, such as cause-effect, condition, purpose, or concession. According to the result of the research, this research area is valuable for deepening our understanding of language structure and usage in the modern Karakalpak language.

Keywords: structure, meaning, complex sentences, Karakalpak language, conjunctions, syntactic structure, types of clauses, semantic roles, cause-effect, condition, purpose, concession, linguistic strategies, language structure, language usage.

Аннотация. В статье исследуется структура и значение сложных предложений каракалпакского языка, не использующих союзы. Его цель – понять, как строятся эти предложения и как они передают смысл без традиционных союзов. Анализ предполагает изучение синтаксической структуры этих предложений и выявление различных типов предложений и их отношений внутри предложения. Он также включает анализ семантических ролей и отношений, выраженных в этих предложениях, таких как причина-следствие, условие, цель или уступка. Согласно результатам исследования, данное направление исследований ценно для углубления нашего понимания языковой структуры и употребления в современном каракалпакском языке.

Ключевые слова: структура, значение, сложные предложения, каракалпакский язык, союзы, синтаксическая структура, типы предложений, семантические роли, причина-следствие, условие, цель, уступка, лингвистические стратегии, языковая структура, языковое употребление.

Аннотация. Макалада каракалпак тилиндеги байламлы сойлемлердин составы, магынасы изертленеди. Бул сүйлөмдөрдүн кандайча курулганын жана салттуу байланыштарсыз кандай маанини берерин түшүнүүгө багытталган. Талдоо бул сүйлөмдөрдүн синтаксистик түзүлүшүн изилдөөнү жана сүйлөмдүн ар кандай түрлөрүн жана алардын өз ара байланышын аныктоону камтыйт. Ал ошондой эле себеп-натыйжа, шарт, максат же концессия сыяктуу ушул сүйлөмдөрдүн ичинде айтылган семантикалык ролдорду жана мамилелерди талдоону камтыйт. Изилдөөнүн жыйынтыгы боюнча бул изилдөө багыты азыркы каракалпак тилиндеги тилдин түзүлүшүн жана колдонулушун тереңирээк түшүнүү үчүн баалуу.

Ачкыч сөздөр: структура, маани, татаал сүйлөмдөр, каракалпак тили, байламталар, синтаксистик түзүлүш, сүйлөмдүн түрлөрү, семантикалык ролдор, себеп-натыйжа, шарт, максат, концессия, лингвистикалык стратегиялар, тилдин түзүлүшү, тилдин колдонулушу.

Functional-semantic analysis is a linguistic approach that focuses on the functions and meanings conveyed by language structures. In the context of complex sentences without conjunctions in modern Karakalpak language, this analysis aims to understand the relationships between different actions or events expressed in the sentences [3].

Complex sentences without conjunctions are characterized by the absence of words like "and," "but," or "while" that typically connect clauses or phrases. Instead, these sentences rely on other linguistic cues, such as word order, context, or semantic relationships, to convey the intended meaning.

The importance of conducting a functional-semantic analysis of complex sentences without conjunctions in the modern Karakalpak language lies in its potential to provide valuable insights into the syntactic structure and language usage of Karakalpak. By examining how complex ideas are conveyed without the use of conjunctions, we can gain a deeper understanding of the linguistic strategies employed in this language [1].

The followings are the examples of complex sentences without conjunctions:

Sentence: "Birinshi kitap oqyman, ekinshi kitap jazaman."

Translation: "First, I read a book, second, I write the book."

Functional-semantic analysis: In this sentence, the absence of conjunctions highlights the parallelism between the actions of reading and writing. The speaker conveys two separate actions without using a conjunction, emphasizing the sequential nature of the actions.

2. Sentence: "Ùyge kelip, kitabımdı oqıyman."

Translation: "I come home and read my book."

Functional-semantic analysis: In this sentence, the absence of a conjunction between "come home" and "read my book" suggests a causal relationship between the two actions. The speaker implies that they come home for the purpose of reading their book.

3. Sentence: "Keshe jumısqa barmastan, ùyde qaldım."

Translation: "I stayed at home without going to work yesterday." [5]

Functional-semantic analysis: In this sentence, the absence of a conjunction between "stayed at home" and "without going to work yesterday" indicates a contrast between the two actions. The speaker emphasizes that they stayed at home instead of going to work, highlighting the difference between the two options.

4. Sentence: "Oqıyman, jazaman, pikirleymen, àmel qılamam."

Translation: "I read, write, think, and act."

Functional-semantic analysis: In this sentence, the absence of conjunctions between "read," "write," "think," and "act" emphasizes the multiplicity of actions. The speaker conveys a sense of versatility and productivity by listing multiple actions without using conjunctions.

5. Sentence: "Jaqın doslarım menen sàwbetlesip, aylanıwǵa shıǵaman."

Translation: "I talk with my close friends and go for a walk."

Functional-semantic analysis: In this sentence, the absence of a conjunction between "talk with my close friends" and "go for a walk" suggests a temporal relationship between the two actions. The speaker implies that they talk with their friends before going for a walk, indicating a sequential order of events [2].

In the examples provided, the absence of conjunctions highlights various aspects of the relationships between actions or events. In some cases, the absence of a conjunction emphasizes parallelism, indicating that two actions are happening sequentially or simultaneously. In other cases, it suggests a causal relationship, where one action leads to another. Additionally, the absence of a conjunction can also indicate a contrast or a temporal relationship between actions.

In conclusion, this study aims to conduct a functional-semantic analysis of complex sentences without conjunctions in the modern Karakalpak language. By examining the structure, meaning, and linguistic strategies employed in these sentences, we hope to gain a deeper understanding of the syntactic structure and language usage in Karakalpak. This analysis will contribute to our

knowledge of how complex ideas are conveyed and the ways in which languages adapt to meet communicative needs.

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